

Effect Of Ambient Noise, Font Size And Character Type On Typing Performance On Computers

Khamaj A, Moosa M, Ameer A. K, Samy A. M

Article Info

Article History

Received:
November 10, 2024

Accepted:
February 11, 2025

Keywords :

Noise Level, Font Type,
typing Time, computers,
Font Size

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.14851673

Abstract

The research was conducted to evaluate the effect of noise level, font size and character type on the typing performance on computers. The data were obtained by measuring ambient noise at five levels of noise 56, 63, 70, 76 and 82 dba during typing on computers by 20 participants. The noise was measured by noise level meter device. We measured the average typing time and average typing accuracy at each level of noise at two different conditions. The first condition is by dividing the typing on computers into three types of characters (Times new roman, Arial, Andalus) and the second condition by dividing the font size into four types (10, 12, 14, 16). After that we measured the average typing time with different font size at different characters type.

Introduction

Noise has been listed as one of the four major pollutions in the world, seriously threatening human physical and mental health. Noises such as construction noise, traffic noise, and office noise are randomly occurring factors and the sound pressure level changes irregularly. The impacts of noise have been well-studied from the views of working performance, [1, 2], sick building syndrome, [3], human health, [4] and emotions, [5]. A considerable amount of research has been conducted on the possible influence of noise on thermal sensation and interactions between the perception of temperature and noise.

Nowadays, computer work is prevalent, and keyboard use is a common feature of everyday life. Keyboard use has been implicated as a potential risk factor for carpal tunnel syndrome and a variety of other musculoskeletal disorders (MSD), including epicondylitis [6]. According to Bureau of Labor Statistics and some other studies, upper extremity MSD associated with computer keyboard use is an important concern in occupational health [7, 8] due to its high prevalence rate. Since computer keyboard use can be characterized by repetitive finger movements, these disorders may arise from cumulative effects of transient loads on the tissue through repetitive muscle activations.

Word processing tasks are a significant part of daily routine work, and require focus and concentration, which may lead to mental stress and mental fatigue. Since it is becoming common in offices to listen to music while at work [9, 10], music may have some relaxing influence on human in reducing job related stress. Psychophysiological stress response has been known to increase muscle tension in repetitive manual tasks [11], and if music with its relaxing effect can reduce muscle tension it could potentially reduce MSD risk. At present, there is no research on direct physiological and psychological effect of music on computer word processing tasks. The objective of this study is to investigate the effect of music and mental load induction on typing productivity, typing force and EMG activity extensor digitorum muscles in word processing task.

Noise pollution in operating rooms (ORs) negatively impacts both patient safety and staff well-being prospectively evaluated noise levels in the OR and found a positive correlation between intraoperative noise levels and surgical site infections, [12, 13]. Intraoperative noise causes distractions during surgery, which may have negative impacts on the concentration of OR staff, [14,16]. The poor concentration caused by high levels of noise may affect OR staff's ability to perform aseptic techniques, increasing the probability of developing surgical site infections. Intraoperative noise affects OR staff's reasoning and their ability to perform their tasks, [13]. Anesthesiologists' clinical reasoning performance was poorer in a noisy environment than in a quiet environment, [17]. Moreover, intraoperative noise may impair effective communication between OR staff, [14,18,19] and ineffective communication is a leading factor contributing to adverse events, [20]. Ineffective communication not only negatively impacts patient safety but also causes increase in stress among OR staff, [21].

Furthermore, ambient noise in a simulated OR generated an increase in the psychological and physiological stress of novice surgeons during laparoscopy, [22]. Besides the increase in stress, intraoperative noise increases the perception of workload and fatigue of OR staff, [23, 24].

This research aims to better understand how people are affected by noise as an accompaniment to mundane, monotonous work related computing tasks.

By performing empirical studies in the area, it is hoped this work will lead to a better understanding of how noise affects people when working and contribute to the development of theories explaining why noise can change people's behavior.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

1. Participants

Twenty male participants with average age 20-23 years old. All participants were in good physical health, no history of hand and forearm musculoskeletal symptoms, and were able to read and write well.

2. Design and Study

This descriptive, prospective, cross-sectional study was conducted and the data were obtained by measuring ambient noise at five levels of noise 56, 63, 70, 76 and 82 dba during typing on computers by 20 participants. We measured the average typing time and average typing accuracy at each level of noise at two different conditions. The first condition was by dividing the typing on computers into three types of characters (Times new roman, Arial, Andalus) and the second condition was by dividing the font size into four types (10, 12, 14, 16). After that we measured the average typing time and average typing accuracy with different font size at different characters types.

3. Research Instruments

An adjustable table (59 cm–128 cm), and a number of 20 laptop computer were used and placed on the tables.

An adjustable office chair with armrest was used for the task to simulate an office workplace. The seat height of the chair were adjusted by the individual participants to their preference, then the table height was adjusted to obtain a relaxed but upright upper body posture and the participant felt comfortable using the laptop keyboard. The noise was measured by noise level meter device. Stopwatch with Countdown Timer was used to determine the typing time for each student.

4. Experimental procedure

This descriptive, prospective, cross-sectional study was conducted and the data were obtained by measuring ambient noise at five levels of noise during typing on computers by 20 participants.

Participants performed a word processing task by typing a paragraph contain 70 words according to the work sheet with students. The time took the typing complete paragraph was recorded for each participant by stopwatch, then compute the average time from twenty participants.

5. Design of experiments

The design of experiences is $5*1+3*5+4*5+3*4*5$ (100 conditions) within subject design. The following tables have shown the total number of experiments with the different conditions.

Noise,5 experiment	Characters type,15 experiment			Font size,20 experiment			
56 dba	Times new roman	Arial	Andalus	10	12	14	16
63 dba	Times new roman	Arial	Andalus	10	12	14	16
70 dba	Times new roman	Arial	Andalus	10	12	14	16
76 dba	Times new roman	Arial	Andalus	10	12	14	16
82 dba	Times new roman	Arial	Andalus	10	12	14	16

Noise, 56 dba				
Characters type	Font size,12 experiment			
Times new roman	10	12	14	16
Arial	10	12	14	16
Andalus	10	12	14	16

Noise, 63 dba				
Characters type	Font size,12 experiment			
Times new roman	10	12	14	16
Arial	10	12	14	16
Andalus	10	12	14	16

Noise, 70 dba				
Characters type	Font size,12 experiment			
Times new roman	10	12	14	16
Arial	10	12	14	16
Andalus	10	12	14	16

Noise, 76 dba				
Characters type	Font size,12 experiment			
Times new roman	10	12	14	16
Arial	10	12	14	16
Andalus	10	12	14	16

Noise, 82dba				
Characters type	Font size,12 experiment			
Times new roman	10	12	14	16
Arial	10	12	14	16
Andalus	10	12	14	16

6. Test Environment

Participants typing on laptop installed windows 7. The data were collected for the time duration that participants completed typing the paragraph, which included also typing accuracy. The paragraph was containing 70 words. Screen resolution was 720*1280 at the same zoom level 100%. The experiments were carried out at room temperature about 22 C.

7. Experimental Data Analysis

The data analysis will be done in two steps; first step is the determination of the most important parameters affecting the response, this will be done by using the response table and main effect and interaction graphs. The second step is to determine the significance of these parameters according to their effect on the response using the ANOVA. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) and of mean (ANOM), standard deviation of the observed raw data, and S/N ratio as smallest the better are carried out to identify the significant variables and to quantify their effects on the response characteristics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figures 1 and 2 show the main effect of noise level on average typing time and average typing accuracy under conditions of times new roman character type and 14 font size. In Fig. 1. The noise level show significant effect on reduction typing time, it can be noticed that, the average typing time decreases with increasing noise level up to 70 dba then increases. The lowest typing time observed at 70 dba noise level. In Fig. 2. The highest accuracy observed at 70 dba noise level followed by 82 dba. This observation correspond the results of noise level with average typing time.

Fig. 2 Effect of noise level on average typing accuracy

Figure 3 and figure 4 show the main effect of font size on average typing time and average typing accuracy under conditions of 70 dba noise level and 14 font size for times new roman character type. In figure 3, it can be noticed that the average typing time decreases with increasing font size up to 14 font size, then slightly increases for 16 font size. The lowest average time was observed at 14 font size. The average typing accuracy was shown in Fig. 4. The highest accuracy observed at 14 font size. These results may indicate that the recommended font size for such conditions is 14 point.

Fig. 3 Effect of font size on average typing time at 70 dba and times new roman font type

Fig. 4 Effect of font size on average typing accuracy at 70 dba and times new roman font type

Figures 5 and 6 show the main effect of character type on average typing time and average typing accuracy under conditions of 70 dba noise level and 14 font size. In figure 5, it can be noticed that the lowest average typing time at times new roman character type then at Arial followed by Andalus. The average typing accuracy was shown in Fig. 4. The highest accuracy observed at times new roman font type.

Fig. 5 Effect of font type on average typing time at 70 dba and 14 font size

Fig. 6 Effect of font type on average typing accuracy at 70 dba and 14 font size

accuracy at 14 font size. In figure 7, it can be noticed that the average typing time decreases until 70 dba then increases for all character types and the lowest average typing time was at 70 dba for times new roman font

type. The average typing accuracy was shown in Fig. 8, the highest accuracy observed for times new roman font type was at 70 dba, the highest accuracy observed for Arial font type was at 56 dba and the highest accuracy observed for Andalus font type was at 82 dba.

Fig. 7 Effect of noise level and font type on average typing time at 14 font size

Fig. 8 Effect of noise level and font type on average typing accuracy at 14 font size

Fig. 9 Effect of noise level and font size on average typing time for times new roman

Fig. 10 Effect of noise level and font size on average typing accuracy for times new roman

Figures 11 and 12 show the main effect of noise level and font size on average typing time and average typing accuracy for Arial font type. In figure 11, it can be noticed that the average typing time decreases gradually while noise level increases for all font sizes and the lowest average typing time was at 82 dba for 12 font size. The average typing accuracy was shown in Fig. 12, the highest accuracy observed for Arial font type was at 56 dba and font size 16 then 14 then, 12 and 10 font sizes for the same noise level.

Fig. 13 Effect of noise level and font size on average typing time for Andalus font type

Fig. 14 Effect of noise level and font size on average typing accuracy for Andalus font type

The Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to estimate the significance of each control factor effect on the response factor, by calculating the contribution of each factor effect. The results of ANOVA illustrated graphically by Pareto chart. Plotting the Pareto chart for effects, gives a very good idea about the relative importance of each effect, so any factor or interaction that has an insignificant effect was eliminated from the chart, as well as, pooled to the error, and discarded from the prediction calculations. The parameters definition shown in table 7.

Table 7. show the parameters definitions:

A		B		C	
Noise Level		Character Type		Font Size	
LEVEL 1	56 dba	LEVEL 1	Times New Romans	LEVEL 1	10
LEVEL 2	63 dba	LEVEL 2	Arial	LEVEL 2	12
LEVEL 3	70 dba	LEVEL 3	Andalus	LEVEL 3	14

Based on S/N Ratio the optimum parameters was level 3 in noise level, level 1 in character type and level 3 in font size, this parameters is 70 dba Noise level and Times New Romans and 14 Font size. Based on standard deviation the optimum parameters was level 2 in noise level, level 3 in character type and level 1 in font size, this parameters is 63 dba Noise level and Andalus and 10 Font size. Based on the means the optimum parameters was level 2 in noise level, level 2 in character type and level 2 in font size, this parameters is 63 dba Noise level and Arial and 12 Font size.

The response table show the most influencing parameters effect on average typing time. The response table for S/N ratio shown the noise level is the most influencing parameters then the character type and the last font size. The response table for the means shown same observed at S/N ratio. The response table for standard deviation shown the font size is the most influencing parameters then the character type and the last noise level, tables 8 to 10.

Table 8. Response Table for S/N ratio.

Level	Noise level	Character type	Font size
1	-44.19	-44.91	-44.03
2	-43.63	-43.8	-44.01

3	-45.11	-44.22	-44.88
Delta	1.47	1.11	0.87
Rank	1	2	3

Table 9. Response Table for Means

Level	Noise level	Character type	Font size
1	154.9	170.5	154
2	146.7	149.5	153.3
3	175.6	157.3	169.9
Delta	28.9	21	16.7
Rank	1	2	3

Table 10. Response Table for Standard Deviations

Level	Noise level	Character type	Font size
1	53.03	59.19	44.52
2	44.33	46.04	45.51
3	53.25	45.37	60.58
Delta	8.92	13.82	16.06
Rank	3	2	1

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) and of mean (ANOM), standard deviation of the observed raw data, and S/N ratio as lowest the better was carried to identify the significant variables and to quantify their effects on the response characteristics, show tables 11 to 13.

Table 11. Analysis of Variance S/N ratio (ANOVA)

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Noise level	2	3.313	1.6563	1.42	0.0414
Character type	2	1.888	0.9441	0.81	0.0553
Font size	2	1.483	0.7413	0.63	0.0612
Error	2	2.336	1.1682		
Total	8	9.02			

Table 12. Analysis of Variance Mean (ANOM)

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Noise level	2	155.3	77.66	1	0.05
Character type	2	364.4	182.22	2.34	0.0299
Font size	2	485.9	242.96	3.12	0.0242
Error	2	155.5	77.77		
Total	8	1161.2			

Table 13. Analysis of Variance Standard deviation (ANOVA)

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Noise level	2	1329.3	664.7	1.42	0.413
Character type	2	676.1	338	0.72	0.581
Font size	2	532.2	266.1	0.57	0.638
Error	2	936.3	468.2		
Total	8	3473.9			

Residual plots are used to evaluate the data for the problems like non normality, non-random variation, non-constant variance, higher-order relationships, and outliers.

CONCLUSIONS

1- Experimental results for all S/N ratio, mean, and standard deviation (real) response values show that, noise level, character type and font size are the significant parameters among all controllable factors that influence the average typing time.

- 2- Based on S/N Ratio the optimum parameters were, 70 dba Noise level, Times New Romans and 14 Font size. Based on standard deviation the optimum parameters were, 63 dba Noise level, Andalus and 10 Font size. Based on the means the optimum parameters were, 63 dba Noise level, Arial and 12 Font size.
- 3- We recommend working at 70 dba noise levels, which observed the lowest average typing time and heights typing accuracy.
4. For the middle level of noise can be use the times new roman character type for low typing time and high accuracy, and the Arial for the lowest level of noise then theAndulus for the highest level of noise.
5. At the highest level of noise can be used time new roman and Arial with font size 12 and Andulus with 16 font size for low typing time and high accuracy, the middle level of noise can be use the times new roman character type and 14 font size and Andulus with 16 font size. At the lowest level of noise can be use time new roman with 10 font sizeandAnduluswith 16 font size.

REFERENCES

- Guan H., Hu S., Liu G, Zhang L., “The combined effects of temperature and noise on the comfort perceptions of young people with a normal Body Mass Index”, *Sustainable Cities and Society* 54, 101993, 2020.
- Szalma, J. L., & Hancock, P. A. Noise effects on human performance: A metaanalytic synthesis. *Psychological Bulletin*, 137(4), 682–707, (2011).
- Witterseh, T., Wyon, D. P., & Clausen, G. The effects of moderate heat stress and open-plan office noise distraction on SBS symptoms and on the performance of office work. *Indoor Air*, 14, 30–40, (2004).
- Basner, M., Babisch, W., Davis, A., Brink, M., Clark, C., Jassen, S., et al. Auditory and non-auditory effects of noise on health. *The Lancet*, 383(9925), 1325–1332, (2014).
- Juang, D. F., Lee, C. H., Yang, T., & Chang, M. C. Noise pollution and its effects on medical care workers and patients in hospitals. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 7(4), 705–716, (2010).
- E.F. Pascarelli and J.J. Kella, Soft-tissue injuries related to use of the computer keyboard: A clinical study of 53 severely injured persons, *Journal of Occupational Medicine* 35(5) 522–532,(1993).
- (BLS) BoLS. Reports on survey of occupational injuries and illnesses in 1977–2001. In: Bureau of Labor Statistics UDoL, Washington, DC., ed., 2002.
- F. Gerr, M. Marcus, C. Ensor, D. Kleinbaum, S. Cohen, A. Edwards et al., A prospective study of computer users: I. Study design and incidence of musculoskeletal symptoms and disorders, *American Journal of Industrial Medicine* 41(4), 221–235, 2002.
- G.R. Oldham, A. Cummings, L.J. Mischel, J.M. Schmidtko and J. Zhou, Listen while you work? Quasi-experimental relations between personal-stereo headset use and employee work responses, *Journal of Applied Psychology* 80(5), 547–564, 1995.
- R.F. Day, C.H. Lin,W.H. Huang and S.H. Chuang, Effects of music tempo and task difficulty on multi-attribute decision-making: An eye-tracking approach, *Computers in Human Behavior* 25(1), 130–143, 2009.
- D. Rissén, B. Melin, L. Sandsjö, I. Dohns and U. Lundberg, Surface EMG and psychophysiological stress reactions in women during repetitive work, *Eur J ApplPhysiol* 83(2–3), 215–222, 2000.
- AORN position statement on managing distractions and noise during perioperative patient care. AORN Inc; 2020. Available at: <https://www.aorn.org/guidelines/clinical-resources/position-statements>. Accessed April 13, 2020.
- Dholakia S, Jeans JP, Khalid U, Dholakia S, D'Souza C, Nemeth K. The association of noise and surgical-site infection in day-case hernia repairs. *Surgery*. 157:1153e1156, 2015.
- Padmakumar AD, Cohen O, Churton A, Groves JB, Mitchell DA, Brennan PA. Effect of noise on tasks in operating theatres: A survey of the perceptions of healthcare staff. *Br J Oral Maxillofac Surg*. 55:164e167, 2017.
- Van Pelt M, Weinger MB. Distractions in the anesthesia work environment: Impact on patient safety? Report of a meeting sponsored by the anesthesia patient safety foundation. *AnesthAnalg*. 125:347e350, 2017.
- Keller S, Tschann F, Semmer NK, et al. Noise in the operating room distracts members of the surgical team. An observational study. *World J Surg*. 42: 3880e3887, 2018.
- Enser M, Moriceau J, Abily J, et al. Background noise lowers the performance of anaesthesiology residents' clinical reasoning when measured by script concordance: A randomised crossover volunteer study. *Eur J Anaesthesiol*. 34(7):464e470, 2017
- Keller S, Tschann F, Beldi G, Kurmann A, Candinas D, Semmer NK. Noise peaks influence communication in the operating room. An observational study. *Ergonomics*. 59:1541e1552,2016.
- Cheriyian S, Mowery H, Ruckle D, et al. The impact of operating room noise upon communication during percutaneous nephrostolithotomy. *J Endourol*. 30:1062e1066, 2016.
- Minimizing noise and distractions in the OR and procedural units. Joint Commission Quick Safety. The Joint Commission; 2017. <https://bit.ly/315brxe>. Accessed April 13, 2020.

- U_gurlu Z, Karahan A, Ünlü H, et al. The effects of workload and working conditions on operating room nurses and technicians. *Workplace Health Saf.* 63:399e407, 2015.
- Waterland P, Khan FS, Ismaili E, Cheruvu C. Environmental noise as an operative stressor during simulated laparoscopic surgery. *SurgLaparoscEndoscPercutan Tech.* 26:133e136, 2016.
- McNeer RR, Bennett CL, Dudaryk R. Intraoperative noise increases perceived task load and fatigue in anesthesiology residents: A simulation-based study. *AnesthAnalg.* 122:512e525,2016.

Author Information

Khamaj A

Dept. of Industrial Engineering, College of Engineering, Jazan University, Jazan, Saudi Arabia

Moosa M.

Dept. of Industrial Engineering, College of Engineering, Jazan University, Jazan, Saudi Arabia

Ameer A. K.

Dept. of Production Engineering and mechanical Design, Faculty of Engineering, Minia University, Egypt

Samy A. M

Dept. of Production Engineering and mechanical Design, Faculty of Engineering, Minia University, Egypt
